

LOCAL CRAFT AND JOB CRATION IN AKWA IBOM STATE; A STUDY OF ESSIEN UDIM PEOPLE

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Abstract

Before the age of European penetration into Nigeria, the local craft had transformed the people in the spheres of technology and arts. This research sought to examine the roles of local craft in jobs creation among the Essien Udim people of Akwa Ibom State. The specific objectives of the study were to identify the local crafts produced by the people of Essien Udim, examine the roles of metal works and local craft production among the people of Essien Udim and the roles of weaving and local craft production among the people of Essien Udim. Structural functionalism was adopted for a theoretical framework. A mixed survey research design of qualitative and quantitative design was adopted for the study. Interview guide and questionnaire were used for primary data collection. Qualitative data were analysed thematically while quantitative data were analysed using descriptive statistics (percentage) Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient with pictures. Findings of the study revealed that the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area used available resources such as iron ore, wood, raffia, bamboo, horn, tin, aluminium, palms, palm leaves, herbs, and animal skins to produce local handicrafts that they ensured survival and livelihood in agriculture, hunting, tapping of palm wine, palm fruits harvesting, food processing, fashion, and other occupations accessible to the people of Essien Udim local government area for their survival. Further findings show that Essien Udim people are well known in Akwa Ibom State for their local technological profession in the production of many tools, equipment, utensils, and others which enhance adaptable and comfortable livelihood and survival among the people. Among other it was recommended that local craft production should be encouraged with grants for more enabled productions to reduce the high economic cost of dependency on foreign goods.

Keywords: Local craft, job creation, Essien Udim people, and Indigenous technology

Introduction

Before the invasion of Africa by the Western Colonial Masters which later led to the introduction of Western products from westernized technology, there were traditional and cultural artisans who produced tools, equipment and furniture for the survival of Africans in their geographical sphere. Before the age of European penetration into Nigeria, the local craft had transformed the people in the spheres of technology and arts (Jayeola-Omoyeni and Omoyeni, 2014). Studies by Manabete and Umar, (2014) confirm that Africa possess a vast amount of indigenous technologies and knowledge for local craft which are embodied in the continent's cultural and ecological diversities. For instance, several communities in Nigeria, Ghana, Egypt, South Africa, Sudan, etc. just like the Aboriginal people of Australia, have

indigenous technology items such as tools and implements, weapons, boomerangs, nets, baskets and bags, as well as watercraft and canoes. In Nigeria and indeed Africa, indigenous technologies and knowledge have been expressed in crafts like farm tools, cooking utensils, weapons and building materials. This technologies and knowledge have been the backbone of the Nigerian society at various levels and these have impacted on the economy of the region.

Studies by Manabete and Umar (2014) have confirmed that the quest for Western education has brought about the abandonment of some of this knowledge, and the consequence has been the struggle to achieve sustainable development from the outside. One fundamental problem responsible for the technological backwardness of West Africa and indeed the whole of Africa is the inability of governments, stakeholders and peoples of the region to explore indigenous viable options embodied in the local craft. A key answer to this problem lies in according to indigenous technology the attention and pride of place it deserves.

Siyanbola *et al.*, (2012) opined that craft is an integral part of Nigerian culture, identity, and heritage. When the market is good, it provides a major source of income for many Nigerian families. Historically and in the contemporary rural and urban sectors of Nigeria, craft is a significant contributor to both local, national, and international economic activity. Craft provides direct/indirect employment to rural and urban people, creating jobs and enabling the poor to sustain themselves. Siyanbola *et al.*, (2012) stated also that the concept of indigenous knowledge deals with the matured long-standing traditions and practices of certain regional indigenous and local communities. Craftspeople are self-employed and invariably work from home. They create employment for family members and sometimes apprentices and journeymen who have been trained in a particular craft. This effectively increases the size of the working household.

Despite the clear evidence of its significance, craft has been largely ignored in any national policies promoting economic development in Nigeria. Although art and design are important for the creation of national and global cultural image, they do not provide the same scope of employment as craft, which involves the production of goods for everyday use and consumption. Craft embodies tradition and cultural identity and it is the primary means by which traditional education produces the material culture of past civilizations has survived. This traditional education includes the knowledge, wisdom and teachings of the communities (Manabete and Umar, 2014). With the increasing pace of globalization, craft increasingly finds itself in competition with cheap mass-produced imports from China and India. This 'race to the bottom' is unsustainable for most of Nigeria's craftspeople, yet they are largely unorganized and disempowered. Craft is in desperate need for strategies and support to enable it to continue its important contribution to society and culture in Nigeria.

According to Manadete and Umar (2014), one fundamental problem responsible for the technological backwardness of West Africa and indeed the whole of Africa is the inability of governments, stakeholders and peoples of the region to explore Indigenous viable options through its crafts. A key answer to this problem lies in according to the indigenous technology and craft the attention and pride of place it deserves.

A sustainable development approach is the process of human growth and development that addresses current needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. The goal is a society in which living conditions and

resources meet human needs without compromising the integrity of the planet. Sustainable development seeks to strike a balance between the interests of the economy, the environment, and social welfare (Robert *et al.*, 2005). The Brundtland Report of 1987 played a part in increasing awareness of sustainable development. Local craft is a function of the cultural heritage of the people with the capacity to give the people a feeling of sustainable development. The feeling of a people in respect of their culture and tradition which define their identity and station in global events propels their desire for sustainable development through local productions. When a people's indigenous knowledge, experiences, perceptions, traditions and history through their local craft are well positioned and invested in., achievable sustainable development is possible. When they are thrown off in favour of foreign ones, it beclouds and endangers the people's corporate survival, identity, and development (Manabete and Umar, 2014). Against this background, this research work is set to examine the place of local craft in the creation of jobs for the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The people of Essien Udim Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State are Annang people who are known for their stride in the production of local craft for both local use and for exportation. Their indigenous knowledge of craft existed even before the advent of colonialism and has been persevered and passed from one generation to another. This expertise in local craft has provided the people of Akwa Ibom State and its environs with house utensils, farm tools, war equipment, furniture, clothing materials, shoes, beads, bags, etc. Their crafts include; shoes, bags, machetes, hoes, pots, spoons, climbing rob, traps, gongs, knives, go-to-hells, chairs, bells, hunters' guns, Jewries, chains, trumpets, drums, etc. These local crafts have enhanced human existence in this part of the world even before the invasion of Africa by the Western world (Essien, 2013).

The people of Essien Udim Local Government Area had survived on the income generated from the production of the local craft until the invasion of Nigeria by the British. The colonial invasion of Nigeria was executed with the introduction of Western crafts which also influenced the market and the life of the people of Akwa Ibom State and Nigeria as a whole, but the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area had found a way of upholding their traditional local craft as a cultural heritage and an adaptive mechanism of the people of the area. The people of Essien Udim Local Government Area have been able to propel the challenge of the Western craft and knowledge into a blessing by the local artisans, who hoped to understand the technology with which the white men employed to produce their kind of utensils, and other equipment. Even though the desire for Western craft or crafts produced through the use of modern technology has grown over time among some Essien Udim people through the influence of the people of the neighbouring local government areas and states, with the building of schools to encourage modern technological knowledge in craft productions and other aspects of life, many local artisans send their children to these schools to acquire the Western knowledge to incorporate same into the already existed local knowledge for the improvement of their local craft production (Essien, 2013).

Throughout the colonial era and up till date very little success has been recorded in terms of improving the local knowledge and craft along the European line. The Western knowledge that was supposed to empower the local artisans to improve their expertise and

knowledge has over the years, not been successful in line with the aims of the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area. Even though Western technological knowledge through Western education was arranged to be able to produce graduates who can go back and take up their parents' local factory and transform such into more a modernized craft production factory, but rather, it created a gap between the desire for local crafts and foreign crafts, some of the Essien Udim people have refused to let down or abandoned their local craft heritage (Essien, 2013).

Today, in spite of the fact that our local markets are filled with foreign products imported from the West and China against availability of the locally produced products by local artisans. Local craft as produced by the Essien Udim people have continually found a competitive place within the local markets both within Essien Udim Local Government Area and in markets outside the local government area. Even though in recent times as we tend to produce more graduates through westernized education who are filled with desires for foreign products against local crafts, many factors still create room for the need for local crafts. Factors like the cost of modern equipment, availability of modern tools in most of the rural areas, traditional cuisines which need local craft for preparation, availability of local craft in local markets for the closeness to the people, affordability of local crafts, easy maintenance of local crafts, and ease-to-use of local crafts by the people with low level of education have helped in motivating the local craft productions in the local government area.

Local artisans and their families in Essien Udim Local Government Area are finding reasons to continue in productions and to compete in the markets with their local craft products. The increased and steady presence of local crafts to satisfy the local needs of the people has generated continuous desires for local crafts across the area and other areas of Akwa Ibom State. This scenario has created the importance of local craft as produced by the Essien Udim people. The importance has witnessed the roles of local crafts in the sustainability of families' economic conditions, livelihoods, source of revenues to local authorities, and means of advancing the cultural heritage of the people of the area. These roles have reduced the capacity and chance of foreign products as driven by modern technology and westernized educational knowledge to hinder the chances for the advancement of indigenous/local craft knowledge. Though there is a disappearance of subjects that encourage local craft production in the school system today, Essien Udim people are finding ways of incorporating local craft knowledge into their existence as a cultural heritage and means of economic sustainability.

With the availability of literature on the importance of local crafts as presented by Essien (2013); Ade (2019) and Baily (2023), there is a gap in the roles of the local crafts in sustainable development through job creation in the Essien Udim Local Government Area and its people. Despite the competitive status of modern and local craft products, most Essien Udim people depend on Local crafts for economic means and livelihood. Against this backdrop, the research examines local craft's roles in the sustainable development of Essien Udim Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The study's general objective is to examine local craft's roles in job creation among the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study are to;

- 1) Identify the local crafts produced by the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.
- 2) Examine the roles of metal works and local craft production among the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.
- 3) Investigate the roles of weaving and local craft production among the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Theoretical Framework

Structural Functionalism

Structural-functional theory, also called functionalism, sees society as a structure with interrelated parts designed to meet the biological and social needs of the individuals in that society. Functionalism grew out of the writings of English philosopher and biologist, Herbert Spencer (1820–1903), who saw similarities between society and the human body. He argued that just as the various organs of the body work together to keep the body functioning, the various parts of society work together to keep society functioning (Spencer 1898). The parts of society that Spencer referred to were the social institutions, or patterns of beliefs and behaviours focused on meeting social needs, such as government, education, family, healthcare, religion, and the economy.

Local craft production has been functional in the form of job creation. This implies that local crafts have become a great means of livelihood for many people in Essien Udim Local Government Area. Local crafts have been functional in contributing to revenue generation for the communities and the local government area.

Methodology

This study examines the contributions of local craft in the creation of jobs for the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. The researcher adopted a mixed survey research design of both quantitative and qualitative research methods for this study. For purposes of the application, the method which was be used in the design includes the sampling approach, which is the simple random sampling procedure. Hence questionnaire and personal interview guides was be adopted as instruments of data collection from the field. Primary data was obtained using the administration of a questionnaire to the study respondents as well as from personal interviews. The questionnaire was structured in such a way as to answer questions in line with the objectives of the study. Quantitative data was analysed using descriptive statistics (percentage) Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient and thematic analyses. Essien Udim Local Government Area was created on the 8th of May, 1989, by the Ibrahim Babangida administration with its headquarters at Afaha Ikot Ebak. The name is a combination of the two units that constitute it namely: Essien Annang and Udim groups of villages (Ibom Yellow page, 2018). Essien Udim people are homogenous. They are of the Annang stock. They are very hospitable, sociable and practice an extended family system. They are predominantly Christians, but a minority of them are practising some forms of Traditional African Religion.

The area is blessed with arable land that favours oil palm, cassava and rubber plantations. The area also has a large deposit of ceramic and bricks. The creative ingenuity of the people is exemplified in the production of raffia bags and shoes, wood carvings, basket making, pottery, blacksmithing, den gongs, hats, mats, local gins, insecticides and fertilizers.

There is also untapped crude in the area (Ibom Yellow Page, 2018).

Essien Udim Local Government Area has eleven clans, 28 wards, and 136 villages with a population of 192,668 residents according to the 2006 Census. The projected population of Essien Udim Local Government Area as at 2018 stood at 288,657 according to the data made available by Akwa Ibom State Ministry of Economic Development, Labour and Manpower, 2018. This makes Essien Udim one of the largest Local Government Areas in the State.

The study concentrated in Essien Local Government Area; it used a combination of stratified and simple random sampling techniques in the selection of the respondents. In the area, there exist 11 clans and 136 villages. Thus, clans were demarcated so that each clan produces at least 36 respondents from at least 2 villages each from the clans. The random selections were carefully done with the aim of having one hundred and seventy (170) men and two hundred and thirty (230) women to be randomly selected without duplication.

Data for this study was collected by the researcher who was assisted by two (2) clerical officers as research assistants. The study respondents were contacted in their residences, offices and workshops respectively. To collect the needed data, the researcher and his research assistants, was first disclosed the objectives of the study to the study respondents and requested their candid responses through questionnaires and personal interviews as the case was. A total of 400 questionnaires in accordance to the sample size were administered to the study respondents, but a total of 359 respondents returned their questionnaires. Some of the respondents were interviewed in English and some the questions was be interpreted in Annang language to suit their level of educational characteristics. The research assistants were trained on the objective of the study and made to be conversant with the design of the study.

The 400 questionnaires was be shared across randomly selected villages within the 11 clans in Essien Udim Local Government Area. The study respondents was be randomly selected from randomly selected villages and the local government headquarters to fill the questionnaires. The researcher intends to visit 5 local craft centres and their respective communities within the Essien Udim Local Government Area that host 5 different local craft centres. A Personal interview was conducted with most of the craftsmen found at their shops, offices, and local factories respectively.

Findings

Local Crafts Produced by the People of Essien Udim Local Government Area

The data collected from the field showed that Essien Udim people are well known in Akwa Ibom State for their local technological profession in the production of many tools, equipment, utensils, and others which enhance adaptable and comfortable livelihood and survival among the state's people. In their quest for adaptation and livelihood, the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area have engaged in various technological drives rooted within the reach of their locality. This according to collected data, has positioned them in technological practice within the available resources in their geographical settlements. The people of Essien Udim local government have made use of the available resources like iron ore, timber, raffia, bamboo, woods, tin, aluminum, palm tree, palm leaves, grasses, and animal skin to produce local crafts which have made survival and livelihood in agriculture,

hunting, palm wine tapping, palm tree harvesting, food processing, fashion, and other professions reachable for the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area for their survival.

According to personal observations, the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area are rich in local crafts, and their occupations in local crafts are shown in;

1. Raffia works and Climbing robs (Ikpo)

Figure 1: Raffia works and climbing robe (Ikpo) weaved by Ikot Nse Inyang youths, Ikpe Annang in Essien Udim Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.

Source: Fieldwork Nya (2024).

According to personal observations and participant observation, the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area have made raffia works a major source of their livelihood. This local craft profession has been passed from one generation to another. The aged population has made it a household pattern of livelihood when they pass it to their children who take over from their parents. Raffia works as a local craft among the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area including climbing robs for pam tree harvesting and other palm occupation or activities. Raffia works undertaken by the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area also include shoes, bags, chairs, tables, baskets, cane cupboards, and others. These have made local craft a known profession among the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State.

In response to interviews, participants narrated that;

We have inherited this occupation from our parents over the years and this has been passed from one generation to the other. We have made a living from this raffia weaving for many years. We have weaved ikpo (climbing rob), raffia bags, raffia shoes, baskets, cane wood, and flower vases. Our parents did it and taught us how to do it. So, it is our occupation and it has become our family occupation.

All of us know how to weave even my sisters know how to weave raffia baskets and others (Male, local craft maker, 39 years old, interviewed on 13th August 2024 at Ikpe Annang).

2. Woodworks and wood carving

Figure 2: Carving of mortar and pestle by Ikot Akpabin men in Ukana, Essien Udim Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.

Source: Fieldwork, Nya (2024).

It was gathered through personal observation and participant observation that the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area engage in a lot of wood works as forms of local crafts for livelihood and economic survival. Some of the wood works as forms of local crafts engage by the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area include mortar and pestle, axe handles, hoe handles, wooden chairs, wooden beds, and other wooden local crafts. The wood craft have furnished the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area with house utensil and mini-industrial equipment for palm oil mills. This wooden crafts have been a source of livelihood as an occupation which many household have survive through its economics benefited for many generations.

3. Goldsmith with Iron Ore

18

Figure 3: Local crafts produced by blacksmiths in Adiasim village in Essien Udim Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.

Source: Fieldwork Nya (2024).

Local craft is a rich profession among the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State. Goldsmiths have made available local crafts like hoes, craters, bells, traps, gongs, cutlass, knives, chisel, hammer, and other iron tools for both house use, agricultural use, and other small medium industries for the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State. The production of local craft by Goldsmiths in Essien Udim Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State according to data shows the local craft has been a great means of Job creation among the people. Goldsmiths have been a household profession for many families in Essien Udim Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State. Personal observations and interviews have shown that local craft professionals like goldsmiths has provided jobs for the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State for many decades. Over the generations, goldsmith has been a prestigious job among the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area due to its involvement in works of art with iron ore and other solid minerals like gold, aluminium and tin.

Metal Works and Local Craft Production

Table 1: Distribution of the respondents on metal works and local craft production in Essien Udim Local Government Area.

Metal works are great Local Crafts profession which many households are dependent on as a source of livelihood	No. of respondents	%
Strongly Agree	189	52.6
Agree	137	38.2
Disagree	26	7.2
Strongly disagree	7	2.0
Total	359	100

Source: Researcher's field work, 2019.

Table 1 shows that 189 respondents (52.6%) of those surveyed in the study strongly agreed that metal works are great source of livelihood for many households as a local craft profession among the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State. Among the 359 returned questionnaires, 137 respondents (38.2%) agreed that metal works are a great means of livelihood among many local craft professionals in Essien Udim Local Government Area. On the other hand, 26 respondents (7.2%) disagreed that metal works are great local craft profession which has been a great source of livelihood among the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State, while 7 respondents (2.0%) strongly disagreed with the question's statement.

Weaving and Local Craft Production

Table 2: Distribution of the respondents on weaving and local crafts as great means of livelihood among the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area

Weaving is a dependable means of livelihood for local craft production	No. of respondents	%
Strongly Agree	224	62.4
Agree	98	27.3
Disagree	29	8.1
Strongly disagree	8	2.2
Total	359	100

Source: Researcher's field work, 2019.

Table 2 shows that 224 respondents (62.4%) of those surveyed strongly agreed that weaving as part of local craft production has been a long-standing occupation among the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area. Among the study respondents, 98 (27.3%) agreed with the question statement that weaving is a dependable means of livelihood for local craft production. On the other hand, 29 respondents (8.1%) disagreed that weaving is a dependable means of livelihood for local craft production among the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area while 8 respondents (2.2%) strongly disagreed with the question statement.

Discussion of Findings

Emergence from gathered data shows that the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area used available resources such as iron ore, wood, raffia, bamboo, horn, tin, aluminium, palms, palm leaves, herbs, and animal skins to produce local handicrafts that they ensured survival and livelihood in agriculture, hunting, tapping of palm wine, palm fruits harvesting, food processing, fashion, and other occupations accessible to the people of Essien Udim local government area for their survival. Further findings show that Essien Udim people are well known in Akwa Ibom State for their local technological profession in the production of many tools, equipment, utensils, and others which enhance adaptable and comfortable livelihood and survival among the people. These findings agree with Siyanbola *et al.*, (2012) who pined that craft is an integral part of Nigerian culture, identity, and heritage. When the market is good, it provides a major source of income for many Nigerian families.

Findings from gathered data revealed that the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area engage in a lot of wood work as a form of local craft for livelihood and economic survival. Some of the woodworks as forms of local crafts engaged by the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area include mortar and pestle, axe handles, hoe handles, wooden chairs, wooden beds, and other wooden local crafts. Further findings also show that goldsmiths have made available local crafts like hoes, craters, bells, traps, gongs, cutlass, knives, chisel, hammers, and other iron tools for both house use, agricultural use, and other small and medium industries for the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State. These findings give credence to Essien (2013) work who posited that Essien Udim Local Government Area is a known area for local craft and indigenous technology.

Gathered data unveiled that weaving as part of local craft production has been a long-standing occupation among the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area. This occupation has served as a source of income toward economic development for families and communities across Essien Udim Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. It was also discovered from gathered data from fieldwork that the majority of study participants agreed that weaving as part of local craft production has been a long-standing occupation among the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area. Findings give credence to Manabete and Umar (2014) who confirm that Africa possess a vast amount of indigenous technologies and knowledge for local craft which are embodied in the continent's cultural and ecological diversities.

Conclusion

This study examined the place of local craft in job creation among the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. Job creation has been the ability to make available sources of income. Local craft has been a major source of income among the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area due to the availability of a high level of indigenous technology and knowledge. Local craft production has enabled job creation among the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area because the people have engaged in the production of many local crafts with iron ore, wood, raffia, grasses, aluminium, clay, and tin. These local crafts include tools, equipment, utensils, and others which enhance adaptable and comfortable livelihood and survival among the people. These products have served the people of Essien Udim Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State and other neighbouring states. These local products have served as sources of revenue generation to the communities and

state.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study;

1. Local craft production should be encouraged with grants for more enabled productions to reduce the high economic cost of dependency on foreign goods.
2. The government should adopt local craft men into government-approved small-scale or medium enterprises to give them access to training and other empowerment.
3. There should be orientation of the masses on the economic value of patronizing local crafts which are made of metal, iron, wood, raffia, aluminium, and tin especially in the present economic crises for a more sustainable economic survival.

References

- Ade, G. (20193). Application of indigenous technology for national development. Proceedings of the 3rd ASUP Conference, 1 (1), 134-137p.
- Baily, I. (2023). Technologies of the self: Habitus and capacities. *Journal for the Theory of Social Behaviour*, 32 (2), 219-237p.
- Essien, U.I. (2013). Local Craft and Indigenous Technology in Etim Ekpo . An Online Publication <http://www.etimekpo4goodluckandgodswill2011.org/brief-history.html>. 17-24p
- <http://www.helloakwaibom.com-yellow.page/2014/09/essien-udim-lga/>
- Jayeola-Omoyeni, M. S., and Omoyeni, J. O. (2014). Contributions of Western Education to the Making of Modern Nigeria During and After the First World War. *European Scientific Journal* vol.10, No.31 185 – 192p.
- Manabete, S. S. & Umar, B. (2014). Indigenous Technology for Sustainable Development in West Africa. *Journal of Education and Practice*. Vol.5, No.37, 54 -59p.
- Omoventi, I. (2014). The Role Of Education In Economic Development: A Theoretical Perspective. *Journal of Education*. 47-52p.
- Robert, D. M., Slikkerveer, L .J. & Brokensha, D. (2003). The cultural dimensions of development: Indigenous knowledge system. London: Intermediate Technology Publication. 43 -56p. <http://www.helloakwaibom.com/2014/09/essien-udim-lga/>
- Siyambola, W.O., Egbetokun, A.A., Oluseyi, I., Olamide, O.O., Aderemi, H.O. & Sanni, M. (2012). Indigenous technologies and innovation in Nigeria. Opportunities for SMEs. Retrieved from <http://www.SciRP.org/journal/ajibm>. 32-40p.

